

Occurrence of Triacontanoic Acid Esters and a Coumarin in Root-bark of *Randia dumetorum* Lam. Syn. *Xeromphis spinosa* Thunb.

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Randia dumetorum Lam. Syn. *Xeromphis spinosa* Thunb. (Family Rubiaceae) grows wildy in tropical and subtropical parts of India. The fruits, seeds and bark possess antelmintic, insecticidal, antidysentric and diaphoretic properties¹. The family Rubiaceae is well known to produce indole, oxindole and quinoline alkaloids of which special mention may be made about quinine². This interested the present investigators to search for alkaloids in the root-bark of *R. dumetorum*. From literature survey it was observed that several saponins of oleanolic acid³, iridoid⁴, glycosides⁵, α -amyrin, β -amyrin, randianin⁶—a haemolytic triterpenoid saponin and scopoletin⁷ occur in this plant.

The present communication concerns the isolation and structure elucidation of three long-chain fatty esters and a coumarin. Interestingly, the acid part in all the esters was found to be the same and was characterised as triacontanoic acid (C₃₀-acid). This is the first report of the occurrence of triacontanoic esters in *Randia* genus.

The powdered dry root-bark of *R. dumetorum* (1 kg) was extracted with different organic solvents in a Soxhlet apparatus. The ethyl acetate fraction on concentration was found to be a mixture of several compounds as indicated from tlc on silica gel. Chromatographic resolution of the ethyl acetate extract over silica gel yielded a solid in the petroleum ether : benzene (1 : 1) eluent. The substance (A) was apparently homogeneous (tlc in different solvent systems) but the appearance of three different peaks in glc indicated the presence of three compounds. Repeated column chromatography of the solid over silica gel and neutral alumina failed to separate the mixture.

The compound (A) did not exhibit any characteristic uv absorption while ir spectrum showed sharp bands at 1720 (ester C=O) and 1105 cm⁻¹ (—C—O—C). The structures of the esters were subsequently established from the cracking pattern of the molecule in the mass spectrometer. The composition of three molecular ion peaks from high resolution mass spectra were determined as C₃₂H₆₄O₂ (M⁺ 480), C₃₃H₆₆O₂ (M⁺ 494) and C₃₄H₆₈O₂ (M⁺ 508). The generation of the base peak at *m/z* 452 (100%); C₃₀H₆₀O₂ was due to McLafferty type rearrangement originating from the C₃₀-acid moiety. As the sample (A) was a mixture of three esters, the alcoholic part was only identified as C₂, C₃ and C₄ units respectively.

Isolation of the coumarin : Column chromatography of the concentrated ethyl acetate extract afforded a compound R.D.-II in benzene : ethyl acetate (9 : 1). It was crystallised from petroleum ether-ethyl acetate, m.p. 202–03°, *R_f* 0.36 (benzene : ethyl acetate, 7 : 3); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 320 and 210 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3300 (OH), 1710 (α,β -unsaturated δ -lactone) and 860 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond); ¹H nmr δ (CDCl₃) 3.95 (s, OCH₃), 6.26 (d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H-3), 7.61 (d, *J* 9.5 Hz, H-4), 6.92 (s, H-5) and 6.85 (s, H-6); *m/z* 192 (M⁺), 177, 164, 149 and 121. The spectral analyses are in excellent agreement with the structure of 6-methoxy-7-hydroxycoumarin (scopoletin). The identity of this compound was established from a comparison with an authentic sample isolated by one of the authors from *Murraya exotica* Linn.⁸

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